

Harmful or beneficial algae? How organic matter secreted by plankton and neuston algae, including that in the surface microlayer and in sea foam, may be participating in climate regulation: a review

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Abstract

While phytoplankton has been shown to influence climate in diverse ways, this review treats just two aspects: reduction of sea-air fluxes, and increase in ocean foam coverage. Plankton and neuston algae produce dissolved organic matter (DOM), which tends to concentrate in the sea-surface microlayer (SML). Fluxes of matter and energy exchange across the sea-air surface and are important in regulating weather and climate. Freshly produced DOM shows marked surface and rheological activity, and it reduces these fluxes. Foam covers part of the ocean surface, largely produced by breaking and spilling waves. Its longevity is increased in areas subject to high biological productivity, and particularly during blooms of some species of harmful algae and may involve specific DOM molecules and the algal genes that produce them. Ocean foam is generally white and reflects about 50% of incident solar radiation, while the foam-free ocean surface reflects only about 5%. Thus, algal DOM helps to cool the planet by increasing foam coverage. Unpredictable changes in abundance and taxonomic composition of phytoplankton and phytoneuston may be adding uncertainty to modelling global and local climate. Further research on the roles of the ocean in climate regulation should thus pay more attention to algal communities, their specific genes and the physical and chemical characteristics of the DOM they produce.

Keywords: climate; plankton; neuston; dissolved organic matter; rheology; sea surface microlayer

Introduction

Oceans cover about 70% of the Earth's surface. At the top, there is a sharp interface between the atmosphere and the ocean, underlain by a surface microlayer (SML), 50 to 100 μm thick. Between the SML is an intermediate layer of near-surface underlying water (ULW) extending down to very roughly 1 m, below which deeper ULW extends to near the sea bottom (Fig. 1). The SML incorporates strong gradients in temperature, salinity, nutrient concentrations, pH and viscosity (η). While the ULW also shows gradients of these and (other biological) parameters, they tend to be much less sharp than in the SML (Zhang *et al.*, 2003a,b,c; Wurl *et al.*, 2017). In addition, measurements made by Zhang *et al.* (2003b) over 24 h in samples from both the SML and from the ULW at 25 cm depth showed η values consistently higher in the SML.

In 25 cm-deep ULW (Zhang *et al.*, 2003b) both layers they showed a diurnal rhythm; they showed noticeably higher η values during daylight than at night, suggesting that short-lived (< 1 day) dissolved organic matter (DOM) excreted largely because of primary production by phytoneuston and phytoplankton increased the viscosity η . This is consistent with the positive relationship found by Jenkinson and Biddanda (1995) between η and chlorophyll content, as well as with the findings of higher 2D compression-dilatation viscosity and elasticity in the SML than in the ULW at 10 cm depth (Williams *et al.*, 1986).

Tumminello *et al.* (2021) investigated sea-spray aerosols derived by wind and bubble-bursting from the SML over the course of a

Fig. 1. A schema of the ocean and the atmosphere, emphasizing the aspects treated in this presentation. Inserts within the ocean, from left to right: micrographs of the dinoflagellate *Noctiluca* sp.; the colonial prymnesiophyte *Phaeocystis globosa*; other dinoflagellates (*Ceratium* sp., *Dinophysis* spp.); bacteria; viruses; diatoms; filamentous cyanobacteria. Dissolved organic matter, more or less colloidal and aggregated, is present throughout the oceans, but tends to concentrate in the surface microlayer.

phytoplankton bloom in an experimental tank. Viscosity in the aerosol droplets (calculated from “bounce factor”) increased up to 1000-fold relative to organics-free seawater, with a strong relationship to the amounts and types of organic matter (including carbohydrates, proteins and lipids) and to chlorophyll *a*.

Values of η in both seawater and algal cultures are composed of a Newtonian component η_w due to water and salt, plus a non-Newtonian excess component η_e due to polymeric DOM

(Jenkinson and Sun, 2010). The SML also is most often, but not always, enriched in dissolved organic matter (DOM) relative to the ULW (Jenkinson *et al.*, 2021), where it is present sometimes even as a gel phase (Wurl *et al.*, 2016).

Ocean DOM is composed of two main fractions: firstly “old” (years to millennia) and refractory, with little surfactant or rheological activity, and secondly “young” or “fresh” (hours to days) biologically and

chemically labile, that are characterized by strong surfactant and rheological activity (Shen and Benner, 2019; Barthelmeß *et al.*, 2021). Likely, it was the second fraction that produced (i) the diurnal viscosity variations reported in Zhang *et al.* (2003b), and (ii) the increased viscosity and foam formation and duration of Kesaulya *et al.* (2008) and of Callaghan *et al.* (2012), as well as the widespread surface gels reported by Wurl *et al.* (2016), and the more exceptional, often light-coloured, floating organic material reported by Flander-Putrelle and Malej (2008) in the North Adriatic and by Balkis-Özdelice *et al.* (2021) in the Sea of Marmara.

In this context, we aim to review the effects of DOM produced by plankton and neuston algae on two important in determining climate. These two processes are ocean-atmosphere fluxes and reflexion of solar radiant energy by sea foam, including whitecaps. Figure 1 shows a schema of the ocean and the atmosphere, emphasizing the aspects treated here.

Algal DOM and ocean-air fluxes

Near-surface and SML-associated DOM reduces sea-air exchange of gases, as well as salts, humidity, aerosols, heat and mechanical energy (Calleja *et al.*, 2009; Mustafa *et al.*, 2020; Adenaya *et al.*, 2021), all of which are important regulators of climate, including storm formation (Veron, 2015). For example, Mustafa *et al.* (2020) reported that SML DOM reduces global CO₂ fluxes by ~19%, and that sea-surface slicks exhibit the strongest suppression.

The specific chemical composition of different types of DOM may modulate these

processes differently. Future studies need to investigate the molecular mass and the tertiary polymeric structure of such DOM, as well as its rheological properties and surface activity in relation to the different algal taxa and the expressed genes that produce it.

DOM-enhanced ocean foam increases planetary ocean albedo

Waves spilling or breaking on a water–air interface entrain air bubbles into the water. These bubbles tend to rise and accumulate at the surface, producing patches of foam (whitecaps).

The decay of these foams proceeds by the coalescence of bubbles as the inter-bubble water drains, allowing the surfaces of adjoining bubbles to touch and burst (Cantat *et al.*, 2013). Draining is retarded and foam lifetime becomes longer if the liquid is a surfactant that binds to the surfaces or if it is more viscous. Relative to their duration in waters of low phytoplankton biomass (PB) or low primary production (PP), ocean foam duration is increased in waters of high PP or high PB (Callaghan *et al.*, 2012), particularly in the presence of certain specific taxa. Blooms that produce a lot of foam are caused by taxa including dinoflagellates *Karenia brevis* (in North Atlantic and Asian coasts Pierce *et al.*, 2003) and *Margalefidinium polykrikoides* (= *C. polykrikoides*) (Vargas-Montero *et al.*, 2006), as well as the prymnesiophyte *Phaeocystis* spp. (North Sea, Kesaulya *et al.*, 2008).

The fraction of incident radiant energy that is reflected is known as albedo. Foam-free ocean surface has a typical albedo of only ~0.05, but foam is white and albedo is ~0.5. Therefore,

when foam is more stabilized by algal DOM the oceans reflect more solar energy back into space, reducing solar heating of the Earth (Stabeno and Monahan, 1986; Evans *et al.*, 2010).

Discussion and conclusions

Different types of “young”, biologically and chemically labile DOM are formed mainly by PP by phytoplankton and phytoneuston. This young DOM is rheologically active and surfactant. It affects sea-air exchange of matter and energy, and it slows the decay of reflectant whitecaps and other ocean foam. Unpredictable changes in abundance and taxonomic composition of phytoplankton and phytoneuston may be adding hitherto unmodelled uncertainty to global and local climate.

To understand their impacts better, and whether they are harmful or beneficial, the tertiary chemical structures of this “young” DOM in the SML should be characterized in relation to their surface and rheological properties, as well as to the taxa and genomes of the plankton and neuston that produce them.

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